

Remote control of ship systems via rogue devices: exploiting insecure fieldbus communication

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Abstract—The main control systems on ships use primitive and insecure fieldbuses for communication. This paper describes a possible attack that exploits the low security of these communication channels to control a ship remotely. A practical example is used to show how much knowledge an attacker needs, how much effort is required for hardware and software and which access options are the minimum requirement for a successful attack. If the attack described in this paper is carried out skillfully, there is currently little the crew can do to counter such an attack, apart from completely immobilizing the ship for the time being.

Index Terms—Fieldbus security, Maritime security, Rogue devices, Attack demonstration

I. INTRODUCTION

Maritime traffic and its importance for international trade are constantly increasing [1], [2]. At the same time, the number of cyber attacks on the Operational Technology (OT) and IT infrastructure of ports, shipping companies and other service providers in the maritime sector is also growing steadily [3].

In principle, attacks are possible via IT or OT systems. Traditionally, IT and OT systems are separate networks within industrial plants – or in this case, a maritime system. This distinction makes sense from a security perspective, as a compromised IT system does not necessarily damage an industrial unit physically. For some time now, there has also been a trend for IT and OT systems to converge [4]. Regardless of these developments, however, this paper focuses solely on OT and specifically on the control of systems on ships and in the marine sector.

One of the main problems that enables attacks against the on-ship OT is the fact that communication between its individual components is often unsecured. The only safety precaution is usually physical security [5]. Furthermore, initial reports are available that vulnerabilities in OT have been used as an attack vector on the IT infrastructure [6].

Systems on-shore and on-board will increasingly interact with each other in order to increase efficiency, lower costs

and travel time. With the transformation to Shipping 4.0 [7], the intercommunication between OT and IT on and off ship will only continue to increase and provide a larger target for attacks.

This paper describes a possible attack against the control systems of small to medium-sized ships by installing a rogue device with access to the respective bus systems onboard. A requirement for this kind of attack is that a physical breach has already happened. Once this requirement has been met, the underlying bus systems that control the ship's functions are easily accessible. This paper lays out an approach to exploit the insecure nature of the underlying communication protocols relevant for controlling such a ship.

The attack's goal is to install a rogue device to take control of the rudder and engine control of the target ship remotely. This paper describes how such an attack was partially tested on a research vessel and what the results were. This type of attack is well known in the automotive sector [8], [9] but to the best of the authors' knowledge, has received little attention in the relevant literature regarding the maritime sector [10].

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section II begins with an introduction to the test object – the research vessel *Limanda*, owned and operated by the University of Rostock. The components and communication methods used on the research vessel for control and navigation are then briefly presented. Section III describes the preparation of the attack. The necessary steps to manipulate the relevant control systems are laid out as well as the workings of the remote control unit. Building on this, Section IV describes how the a working prototype was implemented and which hardware was used to partially carry out the previously introduced attack. The execution of this test and what the results were are detailed in Section V. Section VI concludes this paper and provides an outlook for future work.

II. INTRODUCING THE TARGET SHIP

The research vessel in question is the *Limanda*, a medium-sized ship as depicted in figure 1, operated by the University of

Marvin Davieds is funded through a grant by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK) on the basis of a decision by the German Bundestag.

Fig. 1. The ship in the Rostock city harbor.

Rostock. It is a 15.73 m long and 6.16 m wide catamaran that was put into operation in 2020, which serves as a test object for the attacks presented in this paper. The authors have access to comprehensive installation and operating documentation of the ship's engines, nautical instruments and a wiring diagram. This allows us to disregard the reconnaissance that would normally precede an attack.

Two MAN D2676LE438 diesel engines are used to power the vessel, each with an output of 373 kW. Each engine has its own set of separate networks. The communication between the engine control, the bridge display and the throttle lever takes place via separate CAN buses. On top of CAN for each of the four buses, the SAE-J1939 protocol offers communication between several devices with equal rights on one medium. The throttle lever is used to control the engine speed, and the gearbox is used to select between driving forward and backward.

There are various nautical instruments on board, such as radar, GPS receiver, satellite compass, magnetic compass, anemometer and an echo sounder. There is also an AIS transmitter and receiver as well as a Navitron autopilot. Between each nautical system, NMEA 0183 and NMEA 2000 are used as communication protocols. The former uses RS-422 serial communication, typically between a transmitting and a receiving device. NMEA 2000, on the other hand, is based on SAE-J1939.

Its rudder is operated hydraulically by the captain via a steering wheel. The built-in autopilot can determine the rudder position via a rudder reference unit and control it via two solenoid drives.

III. PLAN OF ATTACK

The aim of the attack presented in this paper is to use a rogue device to take remote control of the ship's rudder and engine controls. It is supposed to be placed hidden inside the dashboard on the bridge of the ship. It may be powered either via one of the available CAN buses or using one of the existing power supplies for the different systems on the bridge. It will be equipped with a cellular modem to control the ship remotely via a data connection to the internet.

Fig. 2. The underside of the throttle lever with four M12 receptacles for the CAN bus connections for both engines.

An attacker is assumed to have at least one-time physical access to the ship and its control systems to install the rogue device. This might be through a break-in at night, a bribed service technician or a shipyard worker. The advantage of such a remote actuated rogue device from an attacker's perspective is that it can be installed long before the actual execution of the attack. The attack itself is then executed remotely via the internet connection the rogue device maintains. The rogue device receives target coordinates and engine control commands that will be translated into carefully manipulated messages, which will be sent out via the various communication channels explained below.

Since engine control, rudder and nautical systems are all separate and use different communication protocols, the following subsections describe the attack procedure for each of them and discuss different possible approaches and the reasoning for the selected ones.

A. Engine Control

Each of the two engines of the test subject has a dedicated CAN bus for monitoring and one for the throttle lever. As CAN has no encryption or authentication mechanisms by design, physical access allows a rogue device unhindered access to the bus [10]. Data recordings indicated that J1939 messages are exchanged on the bus.

The throttle lever that is used to control the engine speed by the captain has, in its original state, four M12 receptacles, two for each engine, where one connection goes to the engine control unit and one is terminated, as shown in Figure 2. This allows an attacker to interpose a T-connector and thus gain write access to the bus. The cockpit displays for each engine

Listing 1. Exemplary decoded TSC1 message

```

{
  "TSC1TransRate":
    "1000 ms transmission rate",
  "MessageCounter": 0,
  "MessageChecksum": 0,
  "TSC1CtrlPurpose":
    "P1 = Accelerator Pedal/Operator
    ↪ Selection",
  "EngOverrideCtrlMode":
    "Speed/torque limit control",
  "OverrideCtrlModePriority":
    "Highest priority",
  "EngRequestedSpeed_SpeedLimit":
    ↪ 1024.25,
  "EngRequestedTorque_TorqueLimit": -123,
  "EngRequestedSpeedCtrlConditions":
    "Transient Optimized for driveline
    ↪ disengaged and non-lockup
    ↪ conditions",
  "EngRequestedTorqueHighResolution":
    "+0.000%"
}

```

are connected in a similar way, so an attacker can access the monitoring CAN bus with the same approach.

Reading the monitoring CAN buses to get status information like engine speed or oil temperature for each engine is trivial. Taking over the engine throttle control is more difficult as the signals of the actual throttle lever must be overwritten, as it remains on the bus during the attack. While there are sophisticated attacks on J1939 known [11] or the native functionality of the throttle lever to have multiple ones connected to the bus for the usage on a flying bridge could be leveraged to manipulate the engines, the authors opted for a more straightforward approach. The constructed messages will be sent out in double the interval of the messages of the actual throttle lever to constantly override its signaling.

To first get an idea of which message is relevant to control the engine speed, a complete trip of the ship was recorded and analyzed. The authors were able to decode 56 % of the recorded messages with J1939 data description files that are available on the internet. All decoded messages had a PGN of 0 indicating *TSC1 - Torque/Speed Control* messages, which fits and is to be expected for a throttle lever. Listing 1 shows a decoded message in JSON notation that contains the various attributes of a *TSC1* message. Further investigation revealed nine different source and destination address pairs. Four of those could already be discarded since only a handful of messages from these pairs were recorded during the whole measuring trip. Others were ruled out because of unplausible torque and speed limit values. The *EngOverrideCtrlMode* has three possible values in the decoded messages: *Override disabled*, *Speed control*, *Torque control* and *Speed/torque limit*

control. Depending on the selected flag, either a maximum engine speed, torque or both is specified in the messages. The limit values of the *TSC1* messages with source 199 and the destination 2 were found to match the expected throttle lever positions by the captain, although the engine speed limits were consistently set higher than the actual measured engine speed. Still, these source and destination values were chosen to be spoofed by the rogue device.

B. Rudder

Taking control of the rudder is not as straightforward as the engine control. It is mainly operated hydraulically via the ship's steering wheel, which cannot be accessed electronically and therefore cannot be manipulated directly with a rogue device. However, the autopilot can control the rudder with actuators.

The distribution unit of the autopilot has connectors for multiple control units, which are used by the captain to set the course. Since only one control unit is present on the test subject, a rogue device can access one of the remaining connectors. The communication protocol is serial and proprietary, which poses a challenge as the message formats have to be reverse-engineered. Because of this and this type of attack on this system would be highly specific for the specific autopilot used on our target ship a different attack entry is used.

To fulfill its function, the autopilots' distribution unit receives nautical data via different sensors via NMEA 0183, which also has by design no encryption and authentication mechanisms. With the rogue device acting as a Man-in-the-Middle, it is trivial for an attacker to manipulate the sensor data such that the autopilot assumes incorrect information about the environment and corrects the rudder input based on the manipulated sensor data in the interest of the attacker. The sensor data relevant for the rudder manipulation is the heading as reported by the Furuno SC-70 Satellite Compass and encoded in the NMEA 0183 HDT message. An exemplary message might look like this:

```
$HEHDT,248.8,T*29
```

The NMEA 0183 messages are a comma-separated list where \$ marks the beginning of the sentence, HE is the device identifier that indicates a north-seeking gyro indicating the heading, and HDT indicates a message that contains the heading from true north. After that, the message indicates a current course of 248.8 degrees from True North. T also indicates that the heading is in True North, followed by the checksum *29.

To now manipulate the rudder position by means of a rogue device, it must intercept the physical connection between the autopilot's distribution unit and the satellite compass. The rogue device will handle messages on the serial connection as follows: If the message starts with \$HEHDT\$, the course that follows will be manipulated, i.e., changed in a specific direction by a number of degrees, so that the autopilot assumes a wrong course that diverges from the set course. This causes the autopilot to move the rudder so that the ship moves in the

opposite direction from the course that was manipulated. So if the exemplary message is assumed to represent the actual course the target ship is on and the attacker wants the ship to take the course 245.8° the rogue device has to manipulate the HEHDT message to indicate the current course of 251.8° relative to true north such that the complete NMEA 0183 message looks as follows:

```
$HEHDT,251.8,T*21
```

It should be noted that the rogue device must not only manipulate the course but also the checksum.

C. Nautical Systems

For a fully remote attack, the attacker needs to receive status information like position and speed of the target ship through the rogue device. For this, it needs access to the nautical bus systems NMEA 0183 and NMEA 2000 on board. The latter can be accessed easily on this paper's test subject since the NMEA 2000 backbone on the ship has one unused M12 receptacle commonly used for NMEA 2000 and can be accessed by the rogue device. The former would usually require physically intercepting the connection between the sending and receiving systems. Fortunately, the test subject is equipped with an NMEA 0183 multiplexer that has one output still available and is fed with the data from the GPS receiver, satellite compass, as well as the AIS transmitter and receiver. With both interfaces, the rogue device is able to access all sensor and nautical data available on the ship, and in particular, the speed, position, and weather data that would be required for remote control.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

In the experimental setup a compact computer is deployed as the rogue device for ease of development and testing. The usage of a more compact device like a Raspberry Pi or even a fully embedded solution is conceivable. To interface the various CAN busses, five FYSETC UCAN adapters were used. To interact with the NMEA 0183 serial connections custom build adapters were developed based on Arduino Nanos.

The communication between the attacker and the rogue device is handled via a server over the internet. This allows the rogue device to establish a persistent connection to the backend whenever an internet connection is available and mitigates problems with changing IP addresses. Between the rogue device and server gRPC¹ with Protocol Buffers are used to minimize the data being transmitted. The attacker themselves, on the other hand, communicate with the server via an HTTP API, which stores the current target position to which the attacker wants the rogue device to navigate the ship.

To navigate to the target position, the rogue device employs a simple Line of Sight Guidance System [12] and crafts manipulated NMEA 0183 messages to alter the direction the autopilot navigates to as outlined in section III. As a result, it is still able to function even if the internet connection

is temporarily lost. The Python library `cantools`² is used to encode and decode the J1939 messages of the CAN buses. Environmental and nautical data via NMEA 0183 channels is decoded with the Go library `go-nmea`³. Finally, `CAN Boat`⁴ with its utilities enables the decoding of environmental and nautical data from the NMEA 2000 bus.

V. INITIAL TEST

While a full evaluation of the remote controlled rogue device is still pending a first test was actually carried out on the ship featured in Section II, but not during a voyage or any regular operation. The intent of this first experiment was to try out whether the more uncertain part of the engine control works as expected. The test was conducted when the ship was moored in its berth and the gearbox was set to neutral so that the engine rotations would not be translated to rotation of the propeller. Furthermore, only one of the two engines was controlled.

During idle, the engine operates at a speed of 600 rpm. To test the procedure for the engine control presented in Section III, constructed messages were now sent to the engine to instruct a speed of 650 rpm. As previously stated the existing throttle lever remains on the bus and continues to send its own commands to the motor. Therefore the rogue device sends the manipulated messages at twice the frequency of the actual throttle lever, which results in a *TSCI* message on the engine bus every 20 ms. Since the recorded and decoded speed limit values were constantly higher as expected, as described in Section III, little to no change in actual engine speed was expected. Contrary to these expectations the engine has revved up to 1200 rpm in a few seconds until the test was aborted to avoid engine damage. Still, when sending the fabricated messages was terminated the engine returned to idle speed and no errors were raised by the engines Control Unit.

VI. RESULTS

This work showed to what extent rogue devices can be used to remotely control a medium-sized ship's engine and rudder. The test object was the *Limanda*, a research vessel of the University of Rostock, in which a prototype was used to show how the engine, rudder and nautical systems can be manipulated thanks to insecure communication protocols. Depending on the subsystem, different protocols were used on the test object. Furthermore, the attacks carried out also differ for each of the networks.

Due to their insecure design it is generally trivial to act as a man-in-the-middle in an NMEA 0183 interface or read and write individual messages on a CAN bus as long as the attacker has physical access. While this allows for systems from different vendors to be connected to the same bus and work together without additional setup, it also enables an attack just like described in this paper. There are a number of proposed security mechanisms for CAN [13] which could

²<https://github.com/cantools/cantools>

³<https://github.com/adrianmo/go-nmea>

⁴<https://github.com/canboat/canboat>

¹<https://grpc.io/>

prevent this attack. These range from various cryptography-based approaches to the usage of Intrusion Detection Systems. While the former offers authentication, data integrity and confidentiality they have the drawback to require additional computational resources and added complexity to the manufacturing and setup processes.

As described above, reading and writing to the data buses is trivial. One challenge with the approach taken in this paper is that existing communication participants repeatedly overwrite the manipulated information. Since engine control messages are also often vendor specific or deviate in some cases from the standard, like in the Limandas case, manipulation may lead to unexpected results as shown in Section V. Still, it was possible to manipulate the engine speed, which in itself could already lead to damage and disruption in service.

In addition to the problems of manipulating data traffic, other practical issues also arise. For example, it was not possible to start the engine remotely because the ignition is not connected to the ship's bus system. Therefore, in order to use the rogue device for that specific ship, the crew must start the engine beforehand. It is also necessary to start the attack after the gearbox is set in the desired direction, since the gearbox commands are proprietary.

Another problem is that individual systems such as the rudder are usually controlled hydraulically rather than via the ship's internal network, which makes a direct attack impossible. Although this isn't the case if the autopilot is activated – only then is it possible to manipulate the rudder via the rogue device. It is theoretically possible to activate the autopilot by attacking the distribution unit and the control unit – however, this possibility was not tested in this work.

To summarize, it can be said that insecure communication on ships is an increasingly relevant problem. Despite the limitations, it is possible to read and manipulate large parts of a ship's system with sufficient preparation and prior knowledge. The possibilities range from simple replay attacks to decoding known standards or reverse engineering partially manufacturer-specific messages.

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